

Case Study

THE PRACTICE OF CONSULTATION-LIAISON PSYCHIATRY AND ASSOCIATED MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS ACROSS TWO (2) CENTERS IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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Received: 23 Dec 2024**Accepted :** 30 Dec 2024**Published:** 11 Feb 2025**Copyright**

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Abstract

Background: Consultation-liaison psychiatry (C-LP) which acts as an interface between physical and psychological health, underscores the fact that some medical disorders occurring in psychiatric settings can co-exist and cause diagnostic delays and missed diagnoses which may lead to poor prognosis and outcomes.

Aims: Our study aimed to explore the pattern and utility of CLP services among inpatient referrals to the Mental Health/Psychiatry Units to determine the associated medical diagnosis and their co-morbid psychiatric diagnostic profiles across 2 centers in South-South, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods: The study was done in centers across two states in a cross-sectional descriptive study that examined diagnostic profiles of 134 in-patient psychiatric referrals of patients who received medical care over one year (July 2021-July 2022) using questionnaires generated by the clinical team, across different medical and surgical specialties. Data analysis: was done using SPSS version 27.

Results: The results showed that most of the received inpatient referrals had a preponderance of females with a frequency of 66.4% compared to 33.6% for males. The most predominant age range was 10-19 years with 57 (42.5%) patients and 78.6% participants below 30 years. Most patients (49.25%) were married, and 41.79% were single. The most common reason for referral from other medical and surgical specialties was seizure-like episodes (19.4%). Overall, the referral rate was significantly higher from the Family Medicine department (40%) while the specialty with the least frequent referrals was Gynaecology (0.7%). Neurological conditions were the most prevalent diagnosis in the psychiatric settings used for the assessment, with a value of 67.1%. Gynecological conditions were the least frequent diagnosis with a value of 0.7%. Conversion Disorder (18.7%), Organic psychosis (14.9%), and Schizoaffective Disorder (10.4%) were the most prevalent associated CLP diagnoses while Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) was the least co-morbid psychiatric disorder with a value of (1.5%).

Conclusions: Clinicians, including the psychiatrist, in the multidisciplinary team must be aware of the risk of medical diagnosis encountered in neuropsychiatric settings and vice versa to reduce diagnostic errors, mitigate morbidity, and ultimately improve the outcome of organic conditions.

Key words: Consultation-Liaison psychiatry, referral, diagnostic profile, clinical, diagnostic errors

Introduction

The assessment and management of physical illness in a psychiatric ward have been identified as a stressful and challenging task [1]. Co-morbidity refers to the co-occurrence of mental and physical disorders within the same person, regardless of their chronological order or causal pathway [2]. Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry (CLP) is the area that deals with the co-morbidities between medical conditions and psychiatric illnesses [3]. This CLP serves as a bridge between psychiatry and other medical fields [4]. The consultation-liaison psychiatrist is commonly referred to as the psychiatry's ambassador in the general hospital setting [3, 4]. The psychiatrist, typically the medical expert in the unit, is responsible for recognizing and treating psychiatric conditions and fostering positive relationships with patients and the other clinical team [5]. Current data indicates the significant role played by individual psychiatrists in adhering

to these guidelines in CLP [5-7]. Recent studies show that 40% of psychiatric patients experience significant medical diagnoses missed, despite not focusing on mental health clinics or inpatient psychiatric units [8]. Medical diagnoses often were the primary cause or important factor in patients' presentations, but non-specific psychological symptoms were also common [8]. The pathways causing co-morbidity of mental and medical disorders are complex, bidirectional, and well-established [9]. Medical emergencies, particularly those involving unusual or psychiatric disorders, may be delayed or undetected if inadequate training and response are not in place [6, 10]. In addition, as individuals advance in age, they often develop coexisting medical and psychiatric illnesses, leading to increased admissions to inpatient geriatric psychiatric care [11]. Mental disorders frequently intertwine with chronic physical diseases, in these individuals, causing even more severe medical harm to patients [12]. A study found that individuals who received initial emergency care had a 30% higher

survival rate compared to those who did not receive such care [10, 13]. Medical emergencies, often causing diagnostic puzzles, can lead to negative patient outcomes, including death, in mentally ill patients and this is of great concern to clinicians and persons alike [14]. A related study found that individuals with these co-morbid health conditions have a 2 to 3 times higher risk of dying from cardiovascular diseases compared to the general population [15]. Previous reports indicate that the majority of deaths in individuals with severe mental disorders are caused by preventable physical diseases, particularly those of cardiovascular, respiratory, and infections origin or etiology [16]. Results of that study revealed that co-morbid medical conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, orthopedic conditions, and chronic respiratory, gastrointestinal, and cancer diagnoses were the most prevalent, while immunologic conditions were the least common [7, 16]. According to a study conducted in Uyo Akwa Ibom, Nigeria, 22.04% of participants had a medical condition, such as respiratory, musculoskeletal, endocrine, digestive, gynecological, high blood pressure, malaria, or psychological issues, with the patients referred from different department in the hospital. Furthermore, the rates of anxiety and depression were higher among patients with HIV/AIDS and hypertension, and the p-values were higher in these groups [17]. Given the above, clinical practice often necessitates hospitalization due to the complexity of physical co-morbidities, requiring intensive medical treatments, and evidence-based psychosocial and behavioral interventions [18]. Psychiatric patients may be diagnosed with medical disorders using prescribed diagnostics, although these tests may be limited [18, 19]. Patients requiring complex or rapid tests may be transferred to the emergency department or other facilities, which can be time-consuming [20]. Medical assessment for mentally ill patients in psychiatric settings typically involves history, physical examination, brain imaging, and laboratory testing [21]. The medical assessment of patients with mental symptoms aims to identify physical disorders that mimic mental disorders, those caused by mental disorders or their treatment, and accompanying physical disorders [22]. Patients should undergo various tests including pulse oximetry, glucose testing, therapeutic drug levels, urine drug screening, blood alcohol levels, complete blood count, urinalysis, HIV testing, serum electrolytes, blood urea, creatinine, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate [22]. Patients should undergo various tests including pulse oximetry, glucose testing, therapeutic drug levels, urine drug screening, blood alcohol levels, complete blood count, urinalysis, HIV testing, serum electrolytes, blood urea, creatinine, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate or C-reactive protein [22]. Other tests, and imaging tests like brain CT, brain MRI, thyroid function tests, chest X-rays, blood cultures, and liver function tests, are also used to diagnose various medical and psychiatric conditions [23]. A study found that patients with a current primary psychiatric complaint, diagnosis, or previous psychiatric history, along with normal medical history and physical exams, have a low likelihood of clinically significant laboratory findings [24]. Therefore psychiatrists should be highly suspicious of co-morbidity when assessing patients and making treatment decisions, as psychiatric treatments may impact medical conditions [6, 24, 25]. This patient-based and process-based integration is usually employed for patient care in CLP and is also known as integrated care. This integrated model, is an interdisciplinary approach that benefits the entire patient and ultimately improves outcomes [25]. This study aims to characterize unusual medical disorders, their diagnostic profiles, and their co-existence with patients receiving psychiatric care across three [3] centers in South-South Nigeria. The article emphasizes the importance of integrating medical care in psychiatric facilities, with psychiatrists playing a crucial role in determining successful medical response and outcome strategies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

LOCATION

The study focused on the Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, and the Military Hospital, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. FMC Yenagoa, Nigeria's largest hospital, in the heart of Yenagoa, the capital of Bayelsa State, Nigeria offers a

range of services including Maternal and Pediatric services, ENT, Orthopedics, and Mental health, Dermatology, Rheumatology, Urology and others while the Military Hospital, Port Harcourt (MHPH), formerly known as Delta Clinic, is a health facility for the Armed Forces, but now offer a varied range of services across many departments like Gynaecology, Cardiology, Endocrinology, Haematology, Neurology, Internal Medicine, Surgery, Urology, Ear Nose and Throat amongst other ancillary medical services like physiotherapy, and public health. MHPH is located in New GRA, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Study Design

The research team conducted a cross-sectional study on 134 psychiatric patients who received medical or surgical care between July 2021 and July 2022.

Participants

Participants were psychiatric in and outpatients, who were 5 years and older, seen, admitted, and diagnosed at two (2) centers, namely, Military Hospital, Port Harcourt, and Mental Health Department of Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, in Rivers, and Bayelsa respectively, all in South-South, Nigeria, who had co-existing medical conditions and disorders, between the study period, were evaluated.

Inclusion criteria

The study included all consenting patients referred for a mental health evaluation, aged 5 years and older, but irrespective of their gender, medical specialty, or physical ailment.

Exclusion criteria

The study did not focus on mental examinations and diagnoses that did not follow ICD-10 criteria, nor did it include outpatient referrals or patients who did not consent to participate.

STUDY DESIGN

Cross-sectional descriptive study.

SAMPLING

The study utilized convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling method in clinical research, where patients were selected based on their availability and accessibility.

DATA COLLECTION AND PROCEDURES

Participants' outpatient, inpatient, specialized medical treatment, and psychiatric diagnoses records of participants were assessed using the Federal Ministry of Health's National Health Management Information System Health.

Facility Daily Attendance Register 2013. The centers had no electronic database. Data was collected and recorded manually before being imputed into the data analysis software, SPSS.

PROCEDURES

The Clinical teams

The centers offered psychology services such as screenings, clinical evaluations, neuropsychological rehabilitation, and consultation liaison services. The clinical teams which included the medical team, led by a physician and psychiatrist, and the gynecological, surgical, and pediatric teams conducted routine evaluations for patients with cardiovascular, endocrine, immunologic, neurological, infectious, central nervous system, gynecological, general medicine, surgical, and pediatric conditions. They also initiated consults as requested by visiting consultants. The research team analyzed socio-demographic profiles, ICD-10 psychiatric diagnoses, and the medical diagnoses made during clinical evaluations.

Clinical evaluation

Participants in the research gave their informed permission to undergo a standardized clinical evaluation that covered social functioning, psychological and emotional symptoms, prior medical history, and mental status testing. To rule out organic reasons for mental abnormalities, the clinical team examined medications, progress reports, and laboratory data. A brief treatment plan was put into place for the patient's hospital stay, and a recent DSM-5 diagnosis was established as indicated.

MEASURES

Socio-demographic Characteristics

Questionnaires generated by the clinical team were used to collect the following bio-psychosocial variables: age, biological sex, marital status, level of education, and occupation/employment status.

ICD -10 Medical Diagnosis

ICD-10 medical diagnoses were obtained from specialist reviews performed by consultant physicians from the medical team.

Data analysis

This study used SPSS 27 (IBM Corp) to perform data analysis. Data preparation and exploration procedures were conducted, and data were examined for errors and quality. Descriptive analysis was conducted for data analysis. Frequencies and proportions were used. Chi-square tests were conducted. Chi-squared tests of independence were conducted to assess associations between the diagnosed medical disorders and select socio-demographic indicators. Probability value of $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Data availability

These datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available because it was used under license, and also due to ethical restrictions clearly stated in the ethical approval letters obtained from the study centers. However, the data are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request, and with the approval of the authorities of the three centers used for the study.

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the ethical committees of Military Hospital Port Harcourt, and the Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, Bayelsa, with access to researchers approved by each respectively. Written and informed consent were obtained from all participants, with consent forms approved by all authors. The author certifies that the study adhered to ethical standards set by the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic characteristics showed that the mean age of our sample was 27.79 years (SD = 12.56), with a minimum age of 5 and a maximum age of 84. Other socio-demographic variables depicted in Table 1 showed that most of the received inpatient referrals had a preponderance of females with a frequency of 66.4% compared to 33.6% for males. The most predominant age range was 10-19 years with 57 (42.5%) patients and 78.6% of the participants below 30 years. Most patients (49.25%) were married, and 41.79% were single. Other values are as depicted in Table 1 below. Figure 1 is a Pie chart showing the source of CLP referrals by specialties. Overall, the referral rate was significantly higher from the Family Medicine department (40%) while the specialty with the least frequent referrals was Gynecology (0.7%). Table 2. is a chart showing that the most common reason for referral from other medical and surgical specialties was seizure-like episodes (19.4%) followed by irrational talk (12.0%). Table 3. is a table showing the frequency of distribution of the uncommon medical disorders found among the study participants. Diagnostic profiles of unknown medical presentations among psychiatric patients showed that

Neurological conditions were the most prevalent diagnosis in the psychiatric settings used for the assessment, with a value of 67.1%. Gynecological conditions were the least frequent diagnosis with a value of 0.7%. Figure 2 is a Bar chart showing the pattern of psychiatric diagnosis co-morbid with CLP Medical and surgical diagnosis. Data analyzed showed that Conversion Disorder (18.7%), Organic psychosis (14.9%), and Schizoaffective Disorder (10.4%) were the most prevalent associated CLP diagnosis while Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) was the least co-morbid psychiatric disorder with a value of (1.5%). Figure 3 below is a Pie chart showing diagnostic profiles of CLP medical disorders in groups. The results showed that neurological conditions were the most prevalent diagnosis in the psychiatric settings used for the assessment, with a value of 67.1%. Gynecological conditions were the least frequent diagnosis with a value of 0.7%. Other groups included Neurosurgery and Urology with values of 3 (2.2%) and 2 (1.5%) respectively. FIGURE 4: Flow chart showing multi-disciplinary approach in CLP. The pictorial representations of the tables, pie charts, bar chart and flow chart are as depicted below.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Participants

S/N	VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	SEX		
	Male	45	33.58
	Female	89	66.41
2	MARITAL STATUS		
	Single	56	41.79
	Married	66	49.25
	Divorced/Separated	12	8.95
3	AGE		
	<10	3	2.23
	10-19	57	42.53
	20-29	32	23.88
	30-39	19	14.18
	40-49	14	10.48
	>50	9	6.72
4	RELIGION		
	Christianity	125	93.28
	Islam	7	5.22
	Traditional Religion	2	1.49
5	EDUCATION		
	Primary	51	38.05
	Secondary	65	48.51
	Tertiary	12	8.95
	Post-Tertiary	6	4.48
6	TRIBE		
	IJAW	52	27.61
	IBO	29	38.81
	OTHERS	53	38.58
	TOTAL	134	100

TABLE 2: Reason for Referral To Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry

VARIABLE	Frequency	Percent
Hyperventilation	5	3.7
Psychoactive Sub-stance Use	10	7.5
Tremors	13	9.7
Uncooperative Patient	11	8.2
Previous Psychiatric History	8	6.0
Irrational Talk	17	12.0
Unexplained Symp-toms	14	10.4
Seizure-Like Episodes	26	19.4
Sleep Disturbances	4	3.0
Learning Difficulties	2	1.5
Hyperactivity	2	1.5
Acute Confusional State	4	3.0
Loss Of Conscious-ness	15	11.8
Abnormal Behaviour	3	2.2
Total	134	100.0

Figure 1 is a Pie chart showing the source of CLP referrals by specialties. Overall, the referral rate was significantly higher from the Family Medicine department (40%) while the specialty with the least frequent referrals was Gynecology (0.7%).

SOURCE OF REFERRAL

Figure 1. Pie chart showing the source of CLP referrals by specialties.

TABLE 3. DIAGNOSTIC PROFILES OF CLP MEDICAL PRESENTATIONS AMONG PSYCHIATRIC PATIENTS

UNUSUAL MEDICAL DISORDERS	FREQUENCY (n=134)	PERCENTAGE (%)
PSYCHOGENIC NON-EPILEPTIC SEIZURES (PNES)	25	18.7
SKIN DRUG REAC-TIONS (Erythema, multiform, scrotal steatocytomas, Urticarial reactions, Steven-Johnsons syndrome)	11	8.2
SEPTIC SHOCK	4	3.0
HYPOVOLEMIC SHOCK	9	6.7
CERVICAL DYSTO-NIA	5	3.7
TICS (MOTOR AND VOCAL)	12	9.0
URINARY RETEN-TION	1	0.7
PRIAPISM	1	0.7
NEUROGENIC SHOCK	6	4.5
YOUNG-ONSET HYPERTENSION	3	2.2
POST-CONCUS-SION SYNDROME	8	6.0
SUBDURAL HAE-MATOMA	3	2.2
AMNESIA (AN-TEROGRADE AND RETROGRADE)	4	3.0
MATURITY ONSET DIABETES OF THE YOUNG	2	1.5
INFECTIONS (hepa-titis, herpes simplex, syphilis)	14	10.4
SYSTEMIC LUPUS ERYTHEMATOSUS	4	3.0
HYPERTHYROID-ISM	4	3.0
TRIGEMINAL NEU-RALGIA	7	5.2
NARCOLEPSY	10	7.5
VAGINAL PRO-LAPSE	1	0.7
TOTAL	134	100

Figure 2. Bar chart showing the pattern of psychiatric diagnosis co-morbid with CLP Medical and surgical diagnosis

Figure 3 below shows that neurological conditions were the most prevalent diagnosis in the psychiatric settings used for the assessment, with a value of 67.1%. Gynecological conditions were the least frequent diagnosis with a value of 0.7%. Other groups included Neurosurgery and Urology with values of 3 (2.2%) and 2 (1.5%) respectively.

Figure 3. Pie chart showing diagnostic profiles of CLP medical disorders in groups.

FIGURE 4. Flow chart showing multi-disciplinary approach in CLP.

DISCUSSION

The findings from this study agree with the fact that the psychological presentation of medical problems must be recognized and unmasked by therapists since physical disorders might mimic mental disorders [26]. According to similar research, non-specific behavioral and emotional changes might be the first and occasionally the only indication of an undiagnosed or undetected medical ailment, which could cause diagnostic delays [27]. Findings from this study showed that masked physical conditions often misled clinicians, leading to misdiagnosis, sometimes obliterating any further medical considerations, and subsequent misapplication of treatment modalities [28]. The findings support the widely accepted fact that disease presentation variability makes clinical diagnosis challenging, even when laboratory results confirm a specific diagnostic entity [29]. The study backs up a prior report that suggested that because psychological symptoms are non-specific, they might be brought on by underlying physical problems [26, 29]. This may be because most people often perceive the mind and body as separate entities, but are interconnected [30]. This makes it imperative to note that in general practice or neuropsychiatry, clinicians may come across different disorders, with non-specific diagnoses, and unusual presentations [31, 32]. Furthermore, acquiring knowledge from thorough case analyses and differential diagnosis requirements is expected to stimulate curiosity in clinicians, encouraging them to think beyond daily practice requirements to reduce missed diagnoses [32]. It is worthy of note that neurological disorders form the majority of the physical illnesses in psychiatric patients, in this study, indicating that many undetected nervous system disorders require clinical care by physicians and other healthcare professionals [33]. Research indicates a surge in new-onset tics in patients without prior tics has been linked to psychological stress, possibly due to the COVID-19 pandemic [34]. The finding that priapism can be diagnosed surgically in a psychiatric setting is consistent with earlier studies that show priapism is a rare and severe side effect of using antipsychotic drugs that requires immediate evaluation and treatment because of long-term issues [35, 36]. In keeping with the surgical diagnosis in this study, a study found urinary retention can occur in patients on antipsychotics, tricyclic antidepressants, and selective noradrenaline reuptake inhibitors, which improved upon discontinuation or dose reduction of the causing drugs [37]. This study found that urological surgical and gynecological emergencies, such as priapism, urinary retention, and vaginal prolapse respectively, were the least common in psychiatric settings due to their being rare in such settings or because of their prompt referral due to potential risks or dangers they portend [31, 36]. This study finding, confirms that psychiatric symptoms can be a manifestation of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), and the pathological mechanism involves central nervous system injury, autoimmune/inflammatory reactions, and increased blood-brain barrier permeability [38]. Psychiatric manifestations are linked to disease activity, medication side effects, and psychosocial stresses from chronic disorders, though their mechanisms remain unclear [38, 39]. This study found that Psychogenic Non-Epileptic Seizures (PNES) are the most prevalent neurological disorder, but recent knowledge has not been well translated into clinical practice, which may lead to long diagnostic delays and poor outcomes [40]. PNES is a complex neuropsychiatric disorder requiring thorough psychiatric assessment, including careful consideration of psychiatric comorbidities [41]. A nine-year delay was reported in previous research in diagnosing PNES leading to the need for clinicians to be aware of factors that maintain and perpetuate symptoms [41]. The implication of these findings for clinicians is that non-specific behavioral and mood alterations often indicate undetected physical illnesses, leading to misdiagnosis and treatment misalignment, as they mislead examiners and hinder further medical consideration [28]. Recent studies suggest that individuals with a psychiatric history or mental functioning and behavior symptoms are more likely to experience diagnostic errors [42]. A common mistake is making a clear medical diagnosis when a condition has a lengthy prodromal period without specific symptoms specific enough

to make a diagnosis [47, 48, 49]. In primary care and CLP settings, these errors in diagnosis can have serious consequences for patients, carers, healthcare professionals, and health systems [43, 44]. Consequently, undiagnosed conditions pose preventable harm, requiring psychiatrists to increase suspicion and improve diagnostic processes, presenting a moral, professional, and public health imperative [45]. Clinicians are therefore advised to be cautious of "premature closure," which occurs when a provisional diagnostic hypothesis is abandoned before its full proof is established [46]. There is also a need for a professional web to ensure proper care for patients with physical and psychiatric co-morbidities.

CONCLUSION

The study emphasizes the need for mental health professionals to recognize and promptly treat unusual medical diagnoses in psychiatric settings through liaison with physicians and teamwork with other medical and surgical specialties. Our study, conducted in a secondary and tertiary health institution across various departments and socio-economic strata, reveals numerous CLP patterns and their relevance to our context. This is particularly significant since general practitioners (GPs) are essential in treating patients with unique or unusual medical disorders, some of which are also found in psychiatric settings. Consultation-liaison psychiatrists are crucial in treating general medical conditions, as ignoring mental disturbances can lead to untreated medical or psychiatric conditions and prolonged suffering, affecting the overall outcome. Therefore, different categories of clinicians have a crucial role in making appropriate referrals, coordinating care, supporting families, and linking them with psychosocial and other supports.

RECOMMENDATION

Hospital systems are crucial for psychiatrists to optimize diagnostic efforts, requiring hospital authorities to put in place effective communication, in-service training, and retraining of both medical, allied medical, and support staff. Designing adequate referral systems and collaboration with multidisciplinary management teams is also advocated to alleviate patient care concerns and reduce diagnostic errors. Providing modern health information technology equipment, reliable laboratory services, and access to library resources is crucial to improving diagnostic efforts, reducing missed diagnoses, and ultimately reducing errors. Expert second opinions are essential, and a multidisciplinary management strategy is highly recommended. The primary objective of these protocols is to make concerted efforts to minimize diagnostic error rates within the best means possible. Primary healthcare and general medical providers' stigma against mental illness negatively impacts programs, diagnosis, treatment, and overall health outcomes. Stigma reduction interventions should involve clients and health workers with stigmatized addressing at both individual and structural levels. Experts have proposed a minimum 6-month training for all psychiatry residents, covering assessment, crisis intervention, psychopharmacology, communication with/in somatically ill patients, and organization of CLP services in general hospitals. Larger surveys on CLP with increased sample size will help generate data that can be generalizable.

LIMITATIONS

The study findings' generalizability is affected by small sample size, potential bias, non-probability sampling, and reliance on routine clinical interviews for diagnosis rather than standardized diagnostic instruments for evaluation, nevertheless, an oversight level is maintained through peer review and ethics committees evaluation.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author confirms that there is no conflict of interest.

FUNDING

None declared.

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Cite this article: Nwaopara Uche. (2025) THE PRACTICE OF CONSULTATION-LAIISON PSYCHIATRY AND ASSOCIATED MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS ACROSS TWO (2) CENTERS IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA. *Japan Journal of Medical Science* 6 (1): 223-230.

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